

Electronic Structure and Spectra of Cyclazines and Azacyclazines : Cycl[3,3,3]azine and its Aza derivatives

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We have studied the molecules of cyclazines and azacyclazines theoretically using the method of Pariser-Parr and Pople modified by Dewar *et al.* Ground state properties such as bond length and charge density have been predicted. Reactivity, ionisation potential, electron affinity, half-wave reduction potential and $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra have also been predicted and correlated with the experimental results where available. Resonance energy has been evaluated and stability of the molecules discussed.

In recent years, molecules belonging to the cyclazine family have attracted considerable interest^{1,2} to the theoretical and synthetic chemists. These molecules contain a completely conjugated perimeter of sp^2 -hybridised carbon atoms held largely planar by a centrally-lying sp^2 -hybridised nitrogen atom³. They were desired in order to obtain experimental evidence regarding current theories and methods of calculating resonance energies of aromatic molecules¹. Azacyclazines are obtained by substituting a nitrogen atom on the periphery in a non-angular position for a carbon atom.

of similarity to antiaromatic systems on these molecules. The aim of the present work is to study the cyclazines with special reference to cycl[3,3,3]azine (2) and its aza-derivatives (6-14) predicting the stability and other properties such as bond length, reactivity, $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra, ionisation potential, electron affinity, π -dipole moment and half-wave reduction potential and compare and correlate them with the experimental results where available. However, in order to complete the studies, other cyclazines (1-5) have been included. Some of these molecules are known (1^{3a,1}, 2⁵, 4⁶, 9⁷, 11⁸, 11a⁹, 12¹⁰) and literature survey shows that others have not yet been synthesised. Cyclazines (specially molecules 1, 2) have been studied by others theoretically¹¹ using different set of parameters.

The cyclazines (A and B) have 12 π -electron periphery. The potential formation of a 12 π -electron periphery in these molecules confers a certain degree

TABLE I—VALUE OF PARAMETERS

Bond	K	A A	B A	Atom/ ion	I_1 eV	χ_0 eV	Z_{eff}
C - C	-6.927	1.512	0.174	C	11.16	11.134	3.18
C - N	-6.9612	1.448	0.178	N	14.12	12.341	3.55
				N ⁺	28.586	16.628	4.92

Method and parameter : The method of calculation is due to Dewar *et al.*¹² following the method of Pariser and Parr¹³ and Pople¹⁴ and it is a β -variable self-consistent field molecular orbital method. Since the method is well known and has been described elsewhere¹⁵, only the salient features would be described here. At each iteration of self-consistent procedure the bond distance (r_{ij}) and resonance in-

tegrals (β_{ij} and γ_{ij}) for neighbouring centres were readjusted using the relations,

$$r_{ij} (\text{\AA}) = A - B p_{ij} \quad (1)$$

and

$$\beta_{ij} = K S_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where p_{ij} and S_{ij} are the π -bond order and the overlap integral between $2p_{\pi}$ Slater type orbitals respectively and K is a constant and characteristic of the bond. The values of A , B and K are presented in Table 1. The repulsion integrals between non-neighbouring centres were not adjusted and were fixed at the values evaluated from the initial geometry of the molecules assumed to be planar having regular geometry with bond length equal to 1.40 $\text{\AA}$. The two-centre two-electron repulsion integrals γ_{ij} were evaluated from Ohno's formula¹⁶. One-centre two-electron repulsion integrals γ_{ii} were calculated using the relation of Pariser¹⁷,

$$\gamma_{ii} = I_i - A_i \quad (3)$$

where I_i and A_i are the valence state ionisation potential and electron affinity of the atoms concerned respectively. The values are taken from the work of Hinze and Zaffe¹⁸. Table 1 also contains the values of γ_{ii} and I_i with effective nuclear charge, Z_{eff} . For non-bonded atoms β_{ij} was set to zero.

Results and Discussion

The bond lengths have been calculated using equation (1) and they have been shown in the struc-

tures. Only cycl[3,2,2]azine has experimental¹⁹ bond lengths which are in good agreement with the calculated ones. Table 2 represents the most probable centres or positions of electrophilic, nucleophilic and dienophilic attack of all the molecules along with the experimental results of electrophilic attack where available. It is clear from the data that the theoretical results are in good agreement with experimental ones.

TABLE 2—REACTIVITY OF THE MOLECULES

Attack of most probable centres or positions			
Molecules	Electrophilic*	Nucleophilic	Dienophilic
1	C ₃ , C ₇	C ₆	C ₆ -C ₇
2	C ₃	C ₄	C ₄ -C ₅
3	C ₁₁	C ₁₀	C ₃ -C ₄ -C ₅ -C ₆ ⁻ C ₉ -C ₁₀
4	C ₇	C ₁₀	C ₁₂ -C ₁₃
5	C ₅	C ₄	C ₁₁ -C ₁₂
6	C ₄	C ₉	C ₁₂ -C ₁₃
7	C ₁₂	C ₉	C ₁₂ -C ₁₃
8	C ₃	C ₄	C ₁₂ -C ₁₃
9	C ₅ , (C ₅) ^a [C ₅] ^a	C ₄	C ₁₁ -C ₁₂
10	C ₃	C ₅	C ₂ -C ₃
11	C ₁₃	C ₄	
11a	C ₁₃ , (C ₁₃) ^b , [C ₁₃] ^b	C ₄	
12	C ₁₁ , (C ₁₁) ^c , [C ₁₁] ^c	C ₄	
13	C ₁₁	C ₄	

*Carbon atom in () represents theoretical work and in [] experimental result.

^aRef. 7, ^bRef. 9, ^cRef. 14.

$\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ spectra, ionisation potential, electron affinity, half-wave reduction potential and π -dipole moment : The electronic transitions calculated theoretically have been presented in Table 3 along with the oscillator strengths (f) and experimental values where available. Oscillator strengths were obtained from the relations²⁰,

$$f = 1.085 \times 10^{-5} \bar{\nu} \mu^2 \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\nu}$ is the transition energy in cm^{-1} and μ is the dipole length for the corresponding transition in Å. On comparison it is clear that the present work is more or less in good agreement with the experimental ones. Table 3A contains the values for the molecules whose experimental transitions are not available.

TABLE 3— $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ SPECTRAL TRANSITION, ΔE (eV) AND OSCILLATOR STRENGTHS (f) OF MOLECULES, 1, 2, 9, 11a, AND 12

Experimental		Theoretical		Experimental		Theoretical	
ΔE (eV)	$\log \epsilon$	ΔE (eV)	f	ΔE (eV)	$\log \epsilon$	ΔE (eV)	f
Ref. 4, 3a		Molecule 1		Ref. 9		Molecule 11a	
3.04	3.66			2.38	2.87	2.40	0.16
4.29	3.86	3.97	0.83	3.68	4.20	3.66	0.62
4.52	3.74	4.75	0.03	3.94	4.08	4.22	0.48
5.08	4.57	5.29	0.00	5.25	4.00	5.42	0.30
Ref. 5		Molecule 2		Ref. 10		Molecule 12	
2.70	4.45	2.46	0.00				
4.05	4.10	4.15	0.56	2.53		2.57	0.00
4.51	4.08	4.68	0.59	3.45		3.34	0.65
4.88	4.09	5.15	0.00	4.79		4.81	0.54
Ref. 7		Molecule 9					
2.14	2.75	2.12	0.06	5.51		5.29	0.38
3.28		—					
3.83	4.05	4.01	0.55				
4.96		4.85	0.48				
5.56		5.73	0.04				

TABLE 3A— $\pi^* \leftarrow \pi$ SPECTRAL TRANSITIONS, ΔE (eV) AND f OF THE MOLECULES

Theoretical		Theoretical	
ΔE (eV)	f	ΔE (eV)	f
Molecule 3		Molecule 8	
2.85	0.20	1.92	0.01
3.45	0.30	3.60	0.39
3.96	0.45	4.11	0.49
5.02	0.36	4.98	0.56
5.44	0.39	5.40	0.04
Molecule 4		Molecule 10	
2.21	0.00	1.75	0.00
4.30	0.59	3.79	0.35
4.70	0.62	4.56	0.55
5.48	0.20	5.23	0.09
Molecule 5		Molecule 11	
2.00	0.03	2.51	0.21
3.22	0.09	4.46	0.27
3.82	0.61	4.86	0.51
4.33	0.57	5.48	0.32
4.82	0.51		
Molecule 6		Molecule 13	
1.98	0.00	3.05	0.75
3.85	0.45	4.84	0.42
4.36	0.49	5.15	0.33
4.76	0.53	5.66	0.15
5.57	0.16		
Molecule 7		Molecule 14	
1.86	0.01	3.72	0.00
3.74	0.39	5.27	0.51
4.33	0.49		
4.68	0.55		
5.39	0.18		

TABLE 4—IP, EA, $E_{1/2}$ AND μ VALUES OF THE MOLECULES

Molecule	IP eV	EA eV	$-E_{1/2}$ V	μ D
1	7.77	0.58	1.99	0.38
2	7.00	0.67	1.78	0
3	7.27	0.45	1.97	0.26
4	7.21	0.66	1.77	0.32
5	7.12	1.05	1.47	1.12
6	7.01	0.91	1.59	1.93
7	7.07	1.01	1.50	1.87
8	7.16	1.11	1.42	3.69
9	7.84	1.42	1.18	0.90
10	7.18	1.02	1.49	0
11	8.24	1.53	1.07	1.92
11a	8.22	1.46	1.13	1.90
12	8.36	1.33	1.23	0.47
13	8.80	1.33	1.23	1.22
14	9.45	1.16	1.38	0

It has been observed²¹ that the values of ionisation potential (IP) and electron affinity (EA) obtained from Koopmans' theorem²² differ from the experimental values of IP and EA by 1 or 2 eV. Hence a correction term is to be added to the HOMO and LUMO in order to obtain the correct values of IP and EA. For IP the correction term is 1.88 eV²³. For EA the value is 1.18 (for molecule 1)²⁴ and 1.34 eV (for others)²⁴ being the difference between the lowest unoccupied orbital energy and electron affinity of naphthalene and anthracene respectively. The half-wave reduction potential ($E_{1/2}$) has been evaluated from the relation²³,

$$E_{1,2} = -0.833 e_j - 3.46 \quad (5)$$

where e_j is the LUMO. The values of IP, EA and $E_{1/2}$ have been presented in Table 4 along with value of π -dipole moment. For lack of experimental values we could not compare our results with the experimental ones.

TABLE 5— ΔH_a , $E_{\pi b}$, RE AND RE/BOND VALUES OF THE MOLECULES

Molecule	ΔH_a (eV)	$E_{\pi b}$ (eV)	RE (eV)	RE/bond
1	91.458	13.600	0.628 0	0.048 3
2	109.640	15.935	0.079 5	0.005 3
3	128.354	18.447	0.067 5	0.004 0
4	109.725	16.097	0.164 5	0.011 0
5	124.051	18.949	0.253 6	0.014 1
6	104.324	16.066	0.059 9	0.004 0
7	99.153	16.219	0.183 3	0.012 4
8	89.986	16.203	0.019 0	0.001 3
9	94.578	16.614	0.908 1	0.060 5
10	94.124	16.383	0.453 9	0.030 3
11	94.289	17.273	0.619 3	0.041 3
11a	94.357	17.351	0.687 3	0.045 8
12	89.725	17.156	1.352 4	0.090 2
13	85.002	17.864	1.926 4	0.128 4
14	80.268	18.557	2.489 0	0.165 9

Heat of atomisation, bond energy and stability:

Stability of the molecules has been studied using 'Dewar' resonance energy and resonance energy per bond. The value of RE has been calculated using the method of Dewar and Harget^{12a}. The values of heat of atomisation (ΔH_a), π -bond energy, resonance energy (RE) and resonance energy per bond (RE/bond) have been presented in Table 5. Since resonance energy per bond is more effective in predicting the stability of any molecule, its value of any known aromatic molecule should be taken as the basis for predicting the stability of other similar molecules. In our study of cyclazines and azacyclazines, the resonance energy per bond of molecule 1 has been taken as the base line for the prediction of aromaticity of other molecules studied here because molecule 1^{3a} is known to be aromatic. On the basis of this the molecule 2⁵ having resonance energy per bond lower than that of 1 is not aromatic. This is also in agreement with the experimental results. Nmr study⁵ also shows high degree of shielding as

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evidence of a paramagnetic ring current²⁵ in the peripheral, nonaromatic system of 12π -electrons. The typically aromatic compound (molecule 1) containing 10 peripheral π -electrons and giving proton resonances²⁶ in the low-field is striking. The properties of diester of 2 show further evidence of lack of aromatic character. It undergoes Diel-Alder reaction and hydrogenation readily. However, the diester participates in substitution reaction⁵ with certain

7

10

8

11

9

11a

electrophilic reagents. But this was not accepted by Leaver *et al.*⁵ as evidence of aromaticity of molecule **2** rather it might be regarded as analogous to those of a typical enamine.

Low resonance energy and low resonance energy per bond suggest that molecule **3** would be unstable

and neither the molecule nor any of its derivatives have yet been synthesised.

The stability or aromaticity of some of the cyclazine molecules (**1**, **2** and **3**) have been studied by Hess *et al.*²⁷ using HMO theory. Their observation is also in agreement with ours, i.e. **1** is aromatic while **2**

and 3 are not.

Although molecule 4 is not known but diethyl cycl[4,3,2]azine-4,5-dicarboxylate⁶ has been synthesised. Comparing molecules 2 and 4 it has been observed that both have 12π-electrons in the periphery. Like cycl[3,3,3]azine, molecule 4⁶ is strongly para-

12

13

14

tropic. This and low energy per bond suggest that the molecule might not be an aromatic compound. Low RE and low RE/bond of molecules 5-8 and 10 suggest that they might be unstable. Molecule 9 undergoes electrophilic attack and Ceder *et al.*⁷ observed that the molecule is an aromatic one. The resonance energy per bond is higher than that of molecule 1. Hence it would be an aromatic compound.

Molecules 11 and 11a are isomeric having similar resonance energy and resonance energy per bond comparable to those of molecule 1. Molecule 11a⁹ undergoes electrophilic attack, hence it should be a stable aromatic compound. Although the chemical properties of 11⁸ is not known yet it might also be stable aromatic compound because RE/bond of 11 is similar to that of 11a.

Molecule 12 is known as 2-methyl-4-carboethoxy-1,3,6,7-tetraazacyl[3,3,3]azine¹⁰. It undergoes electrophilic attack. It might be an aromatic compound. But the molecule is less stable¹⁰ than of 9, though resonance energy and RE per bond of 12 are greater than those of 9.

Although molecules 13 and 14 have not yet been synthesised yet their high resonance energy and resonance energy per bond suggest that they might be stable aromatic compound.

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